

Supporting results for PRE-HLB Deliverable 5.2

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1 Introduction

This document collates additional supporting results for Deliverable 5.2 “Simulation results to predict likely invasion of vectors and HLB disease into and across EU states” for the PRE-HLB (Preventing HLB epidemics for ensuring citrus survival in Europe) project.

The document supplied as a deliverable for Work Package 5.2 described the results of applying a simulation model of the spread of HLB and its vector within three 50 km × 50 km regions in Spain and Portugal: Valencia, Andalusia and the Algarve.

In each region, the model was used to assess management efficacy under two distinct epidemiological scenarios

- Scenario One. Early control and potential eradication of an isolated outbreak, testing disease management strategies to be applied following the first detection of the pathogen.
- Scenario Two. Sustained control of an ongoing, established epidemic, testing cases in which the focal area is embedded in a larger region within which disease is already well-established, and so where the pathogen is continually being introduced into the region.

The results of both scenarios for all three regions were summarised in the deliverable document, including a sensitivity analysis to parameters controlling management efficacy. However, detailed maps showing spread were only provided in the main deliverable for Valencia under Scenario One. This document collates these results for Scenario Two in Valencia, and for both Scenarios in Andalusia and the Algarve.

2 Valencia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic)

Figure 1. Valencia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). A single example of the spread of HLB over 10 years without control and with a primary infection rate of 3 per year. Maps show the proportion of the cell that contains infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell.

Figure 2. Valencia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). A single example of the spread of HLB over 20 years in scenario 2. Maps show the density of infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell. In this example, all commercial citrus were inspected every 6 months, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$. Any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate and a 90% roguing probability.

Figure 3. Valencia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 4. Valencia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 5. Valencia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with 100% compliance.

Figure 6. Valencia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). The percentage of cells with at least one infected unit of citrus (yellow) and the percentage of all citrus infected (blue), for the no roguing case, the case where only commercial citrus is inspected and rogued (see Figs. 2 and 3), the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued (see Fig. 4), and the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued with 100% compliance and a 100% roguing probability (see Fig. 5). Shaded regions show the 95% prediction interval of the simulation results.

3 Andalusia: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction)

Figure 7. Andalusia: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). A single example of the spread of HLB in Andalusia over 10 years without control and with a primary infection rate of 3 per year. Maps show the proportion of the cell that contains infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell.

Figure 8. Andalusia: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). A single example of the spread of HLB over 20 years in scenario 2. Maps show the density of infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell. In this example, all commercial citrus were inspected every 6 months, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$. Any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate and a 90% roguing probability.

Figure 9. Andalusia: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 10. Andalusia: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 11. Andalusia: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with 100% compliance.

Figure 12. Andalusia: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). The percentage of cells with at least one infected unit of citrus (yellow) and the percentage of all citrus infected (blue), for the no roguing case, the case where only commercial citrus is inspected and rogued (see Figs. 8 and 9), the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued (see Fig. 10), and the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued with 100% compliance and a 100% roguing probability (see Fig. 11). Shaded regions show the 95% prediction interval of the simulation results.

4 Andalusia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic)

Figure 13. Andalusia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). A single example of the spread of HLB in Andalusia over 10 years without control and with a primary infection rate of 3 per year. Maps show the proportion of the cell that contains infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell.

Figure 14. Andalusia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). A single example of the spread of HLB over 20 years in scenario 2. Maps show the density of infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell. In this example, all commercial citrus were inspected every 6 months, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$. Any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate and a 90% roguing probability.

Figure 15. Andalusia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 16. Andalusia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 17. Andalusia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with 100% compliance.

Figure 18. Andalusia: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). The percentage of cells with at least one infected unit of citrus (yellow) and the percentage of all citrus infected (blue), for the no roguing case, the case where only commercial citrus is inspected and rogued (see Figs. 14 and 15), the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued (see Fig. 16), and the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued with 100% compliance and a 100% roguing probability (see Fig. 17). Shaded regions show the 95% prediction interval of the simulation results.

5 Algarve: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction)

Figure 19. Algarve: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). A single example of the spread of HLB in Algarve over 10 years without control and with a primary infection rate of 3 per year. Maps show the proportion of the cell that contains infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell.

Figure 20. Algarve: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). A single example of the spread of HLB over 20 years in scenario 2. Maps show the density of infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell. In this example, all commercial citrus were inspected every 6 months, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$. Any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate and a 90% roguing probability.

Figure 21. Algarve: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 22. Algarve: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 23. Algarve: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with 100% compliance.

Figure 24. Algarve: Scenario One (Isolated Introduction). The percentage of cells with at least one infected unit of citrus (yellow) and the percentage of all citrus infected (blue), for the no roguing case, the case where only commercial citrus is inspected and rogued (see Figs. 20 and 21), the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued (see Fig. 22), and the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued with 100% compliance and a 100% roguing probability (see Fig. 23). Shaded regions show the 95% prediction interval of the simulation results.

6 Algarve: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic)

Figure 25. Algarve: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). A single example of the spread of HLB in Algarve over 10 years without control and with a primary infection rate of 3 per year. Maps show the proportion of the cell that contains infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell.

Figure 26. Algarve: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). A single example of the spread of HLB over 20 years in scenario 2. Maps show the density of infected citrus ($E + C + I$) per grid cell. In this example, all commercial citrus were inspected every 6 months, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$. Any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate and a 90% roguing probability.

Figure 27. Algarve: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued, with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 28. Algarve: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with a 90% compliance rate.

Figure 29. Algarve: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). Probability of each cell being infected by HLB within 20 years (left) and the mean time that infection first occurred (right). Five units within 1% of cells containing commercial citrus were each inspected once per year, with a probability of detection $P = 0.5$, until the disease was first detected. Then all commercial and residential units were inspected once every six months and any symptomatic citrus was rogued with 100% compliance.

Figure 30. Algarve: Scenario Two (Established Epidemic). The percentage of cells with at least one infected unit of citrus (yellow) and the percentage of all citrus infected (blue), for the no roguing case, the case where only commercial citrus is inspected and rogued (see Figs. 26 and 27), the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued (see Fig. 28), and the case where commercial and residential citrus are inspected and rogued with 100% compliance and a 100% roguing probability (see Fig. 29). Shaded regions show the 95% prediction interval of the simulation results.